

Business Model and Sustainability Perspectives Framework for ICT – Illustrated by Joint Communications and Sensing in 6G

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Abstract: Business models and sustainability perspectives lay the groundwork for the development of new information and communication technology (ICT) solutions. Business model antecedents – opportunity, value, and advantage – can align with sustainability perspectives, for both sustainable ICT and ICT for sustainability dimensions, and considering the environmental, social, and economic pillars of sustainability. This paper proposes a comprehensive framework for examining business models and sustainability perspectives in the context of ICTs, where the development of the sixth generation (6G) mobile communications systems is at heart. The framework integrates business model antecedents with the key pillars and dimensions of sustainability. The contribution of this paper lies in offering a holistic approach to studying business models and sustainability in ICT, highlighting the potential of emerging 6G technologies, particularly joint communications and sensing, to support sustainable development.

Keywords: business model, sustainability, ICT, joint communications and sensing, 6G.

Introduction

The grand challenge of sustainability has entered the business model discussion (e.g., Esau et al., 2025) for real, also in the context of information and communications technology (ICT) solutions (Matinmikko-Blue et al., 2023, Wikström et al., 2024). The extant literature on business models and sustainability presents two distinct yet interconnected perspectives. The broader body of work centers around *sustainable business models* (Atkova et al., 2025; Huang & Zhou, 2025; Bennett & Grabs, 2025), emphasizing how businesses can align their operations with sustainable practices, primarily focusing on long-term value creation. The *business models for sustainability* are more concerned with fostering sustainability impacts through business practices and tend to concentrate on environmental sustainability. This narrow focus overshadows the critical need to address social and economic sustainability pillars, which are also essential for creating a holistic and balanced approach to sustainability in business model discussions.

The ICT industry is essential for driving digital transformation, fostering economic development, and empowering individuals (Hedman & Kalling, 2003). As with the business models, sustainability in ICT has been approached as ICT being *sustainable per se* (i.e., sustainable ICT) or it being *enabler for sustainability* (i.e., ICT for sustainability) (Bocken, 2023; Cantele & Truzzi, 2020). In recent discussions (Matinmikko-Blue et al., 2024, Hexa-X-II, June 2023; Wikström et al., 2024; Zhang & Wei, 2022; Charfeddine & Umlai, 2023; Qadri et al., 2025), the sustainability in ICT has been expanded from environmental sustainability to consider jointly the environmental, social, and economic sustainability pillars. At the same time, it is remarkable that the energy consumption of the digital economy rises proportionately to the revenue it generates, exposing detrimental sustainability effects (Little, 2021). Thus, paradoxically, the ICT industry appears to be both a driver and a challenge for sustainability.

To address this paradox, the business model research provides the necessary conceptual space to integrate the ICT-related and business model-related sustainability discussions (c.f., Adisa et al., 2024). Yet, there is very little work bringing together the key elements from business model, sustainability and ICT domains (Hexa-X-II, December 2023). At the business model side, this paper focuses on the business model antecedents – opportunities, value, and advantages (Foss & Saebi, 2017) – to incorporate sustainability in business models. At the sustainability side, the paper focuses on environmental, social, and economic sustainability pillars in the development and use of ICTs (Matinmikko-Blue et al., 2024, Wikstöm et al., 2024). The research question set for the paper is as follows:

RQ: How do business model antecedents relate to sustainability in the ICT context?

To answer this question the paper aims first to redefine the business model antecedents-related discussion to accommodate sustainability-related analysis. Second, the paper will conceptualize the sustainability effects related to ICTs through environmental, social, and economic sustainability pillars. The targeted main contribution of the paper is a framework that integrates business model antecedents, opportunities, value, and advantages to sustainability perspectives including the dimensions of sustainable ICT and ICT for sustainability and environmental, social, and economic sustainability pillars. The paper will also provide an illustrative example of ICTs using specific joint communications and sensing technology in

future 6G mobile communications.

The structure of the paper is as follows. It first presents the method that consists of the theoretical background of business model antecedents and sustainability and the 6G context. It then proceeds to present the main results, which includes a framework with redefined the main business model antecedents, and their mapping to key sustainability dimensions and pillars, followed by an illustrative example of joint communications and sensing in 6G. Finally, the conclusion synthesizes the discussion and highlights the practical implications of the key results, emphasizing the novelty of the paper

Method

This section presents the conceptual approach of the research, centering on the business model approach and sustainability in ICTs and the relevant context of 6G. Figure 1 depicts the approach of the paper. On the left side, the business model approach of the paper concerns sustainable business models and business models for sustainability and opportunity, value, and advantage as business model antecedents. On the right side, the sustainability discussions in ICT recognize sustainable ICT and ICT for sustainability dimensions and the environmental, social, and economic sustainability pillars.

Figure 1. Perspectives on business models and sustainability in ICT.

Business model antecedents and sustainability

The business model approach is framed by business model antecedents and outcomes (Foss & Saebi, 2017). Though the concept of a business model is continuously debated, the scholars converge on the idea that there are three constructs fundamental to understanding of business models– opportunity, value and advantage. Whether discovered or created (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000; Alvarez & Barney, 2007), opportunity can be regarded as the antecedent to any business model (Atkova, 2018) as, without an opportunity, there is little point in creating a business model in the first place; the main function of a business model is to explore and

exploit opportunities (Atkova, 2018; Teece 2010).

The processes of value creation, delivery, and capture (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010; Foss & Saebi, 2017; Amit & Han, 2017), value co-creation and co-capture (Bengtsson & Kock, 2000), and even value sharing (Verstraete & Jouison-Laffitte, 2011), have constituted the foundational part of the business model construct. Essentially, the business model depicts company value processes through opportunity exploration and exploitation, aiming at creating a competitive advantage and improving company performance (Amit & Zott 2001; George & Bock, 2011; Chesbrough, 2010). In other words, the business model can be seen as a vehicle for creating competitive advantage through opportunity exploration and exploitation. Together with opportunity, competitive advantage allows linking the business model to the external business environment (Ahokangas & Myllykoski, 2014).

Broadening the notion of value to include the aspects of sustainability has created the foundations for a rapidly expanding discussion on sustainable business models and business models for sustainability (Cantele & Truzzi, 2020). Sustainable business models take a holistic view of business operations, considering economic, environmental, and social aspects, as well as the needs of all stakeholders, including nature (Bocken, 2023). Business models for sustainability focus on creating value for various stakeholders and the environment, with a core logic built on reinforcing feedback loops between customer value, firm value, and social, environmental and economic value (Abdelkafi & Täuscher, 2016).

Sustainability in ICTs

Sustainability in ICTs is characterized by two dimensions – sustainable ICT and ICT for sustainability – as shown in Figure 1. The first focuses on the direct first-order effects that occur from the development and deployment of the ICT solution itself while the latter concerns the indirect effects of the use of ICTs. Sustainability discussions in the ICT context today consider three interconnected pillars – the environmental, social, and economic sustainability (Matinmikko-Blue et al., 2024, Hexa-X-II, June 2023). Environmental sustainability focuses on preserving natural resources and ecosystems through efficient resource use, waste reduction, and minimizing pollution, among others. Achieving this calls for renewable energy, environmental practices, and policies that promote environmental sustainability. (Hexa-X-II, June 2023). Social sustainability prioritizes the well-being of individuals and communities, emphasizing topics like equity, inclusion, and equal access to resources. It fosters social cohesion by promoting trust, cooperation, and shared values, with key issues such as digital inclusion and trustworthiness (Hexa-X-II, June 2023). Economic sustainability focuses on achieving long-term growth, efficiency improvements, and cost reductions while respecting environmental and social sustainability pillars. (Hexa-X-II, June 2023).

The ICT context: Joint communications and sensing in 6G

ICTs can help in solving sustainability challenges through monitoring, data analysis and related decision making. Data analytics platforms, leveraging contextualized data from ICTs including mobile networks, can provide valuable insights and support the development of sustainable

practices. An important development direction in ICTs is the mobile communications where the next generation 6G systems are under development, aiming at deployment in 2030s.

Future 6G mobile communications systems aim to create accurate situational awareness of the environment and operations with the help of new joint communications and sensing technologies. This concept involves utilizing radio signals transmitted and received by network elements to detect the presence, shape, location, and movement speed of objects. Sensing technologies can detect targets such as uncrewed aerial vehicles, humans, automobiles, etc. To provide a comprehensive sensing solution for the 6G era, sensor fusion will be needed, combining network sensing data with information from other sensors and sources, such as location tags or sensors commonly found in devices like accelerometers, gyroscopes, and cameras. This enables real-time environmental modeling, facilitating early risk and disaster detection, and optimizing response efforts. By combining these advancements with appropriate service exposure, new sustainable business models can emerge, particularly in sectors such as smart cities and communities. The major standardization body in mobile communications, 3GPP, has identified several use cases that make use of the new joint communications and sensing technology (3GPP, 2025). Identified use cases target various applications, including identifying vehicle trajectories, factory automation to detect moving objects, consumer traffic monitoring to monitor congestion, automotive maneuvering and navigation to detect pedestrians, intruder detection in premises, environment monitoring, health monitoring, and localization of spatial location of objects, among others.

Key results

Theorizing with the business model and sustainability perspectives in ICT

Extant business model literature identifies and establishes the connections between the business model antecedents of opportunity, value, and advantage (Zott & Amit, 2010; Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010; Ahokangas & Myllykoski, 2014). A practical challenge is how to tell the difference between the three in empirical research: when, in what conditions, and how does an *opportunity* to create value turn into *actual* value creation? And, when, in what conditions, and how does the created *value* turn into a competitive *advantage*? Opportunities for stakeholders and the whole ecosystem emerge when there is complementarity and synergy among stakeholders (Jacobides et al., 2018). Value, in turn, is interactively co-created and is both internal to each stakeholder and within the whole ecosystem. Advantages glue the ecosystem together and protect against outside competition. Fundamentally, an opportunity refers to *potential* for value creation.

Thus, in the context of sustainability, we define **opportunity as a situation for addressing sustainability challenges while capturing value with ecosystem stakeholders**. Value, in turn, refers to something that has become *actualized* and has material *outcomes*. Thus, we define **value creation as establishing premises for positive outcomes for ecosystem stakeholders**. Finally, advantages can be considered as *intensive*, to make a difference or stand out in competition. Thus, we define **advantages as unique outcomes that enable leveraging long-term value capture, positive externalities among ecosystem stakeholders, and create spillover effects beyond ecosystem boundaries**.

In parallel with the discussion on sustainable business models and business models for sustainability, extant literature on sustainability and ICTs distinguishes two inter-related directions: sustainable ICT and ICT for sustainability. Regarding environmental sustainability, extant literature (ITU-T, 2022) defines **first-order effects as the direct environmental effect associated with the physical existence of an ICT solution**, which we here assume to consider all three sustainability pillars – environmental, social, and economic sustainability. **Second-order effects as presented in (ITU-T, 2022) are the indirect impact created by the use and application of ICTs**, which we adopt here.

Table 1 presents the key findings of the paper for business model antecedents – opportunity, value and advantage based on the presented definitions – against the first and second order environmental, social and economic effects of ICTs. The first order environmental effects-related *opportunities* concern building and developing resource-effective solutions and solutions for environmental impact assessments. The second-order environmental effects include the use of these solutions. First-order social sustainability may mean promoting inclusiveness, equality, and diversity of actors in ICT development and complying with regulations. Second-order social sustainability effects may include bridging the digital divide and providing access to relevant digital services to enhance wellbeing, empowering people, and ensuring proper data privacy, security, and AI regulation compliance. Opportunities for creating first-order economic sustainability effects include improving effectiveness and efficiency for the developers and providers of ICT solutions and creating new markets for technologies and services. The second-order economic sustainability effects mean taking the same effects to other sectors through the use of ICT solutions.

Regarding *value creation*, the first-order environmental sustainability effects may be exemplified by promoting circularity and reducing resource consumption in ICT while the second-order effects may mean enabling circularity and bringing the value created by sustainable ICT to other sectors. First-order social sustainability effects, in turn, may mean promoting human-centricity and other values in ICT development, while promoting co-operative ownership of solutions and public-private-people partnerships. Second-order effects, again, concern the utilization of ICT for social sustainability-enhancing activities. From the economic viewpoint, first-order effects could concern promoting cost reduction and new revenue generation for ICT, and regarding second-order effects, to other sectors and providing data for environmental and social development.

Finally, environmental first-order *advantages* include the availability and transparency of sustainability reporting data in compliance with regulations and optimized operations based on such data. Regarding the second order effects, the existing sustainability reporting data should help other sectors, too. Shared information should help other sectors to make informed decisions and optimize their operations. Social first-order effects mean maintained human values and transparent governance while second-order effects may mean the achieved digital inclusion and the availability of life-enhancing services. Economically, the first-order advantage-related effects may mean access to global markets, and consequently, new revenues. Regarding the second-order effects, cost reductions, efficiency improvements while minimizing resource usage, and new revenue generation with the use of ICT should be achieved.

Table 1. Framework for bringing together business model antecedents and sustainability perspectives in ICTs.

Business Model Antecedents	Environmental Sustainability		Social sustainability		Economic sustainability	
	1 st order environmental effect	2 nd order environmental effect	1 st order social sustainability effect	2 nd order social sustainability effect	1 st order economic sustainability effect	2 nd order economic sustainability effect
Opportunity (a situation for addressing sustainability challenges while capturing value with ecosystem stakeholders)	Build ICT solutions that minimize resource consumption (incl. energy) and/or harm to environment. Develop ICT solutions for environmental impact assessments to comply with the regulations.	Use of ICT solutions for reducing resource consumption of other sectors. Use of ICT solutions environmental impact assessments to comply with the regulations.	Promote the inclusiveness, equality and diversity of actors in ICT development. Improve working conditions and empower developers in ICT sector. Comply with data privacy and security, and AI regulations.	Bridge the digital divide and provide access to relevant digital services to enhance wellbeing and empower people. Promote trustworthiness, privacy, security, and trust. Ensure proper use of data privacy and security, AI regulation.	Improve effectiveness and efficiency for the developers and providers of ICT solutions. Create new markets for technologies and services.	Improve effectiveness and efficiency in other sectors. Create new markets for technologies and services.
Value creation (establishing premises for positive outcomes for ecosystem stakeholders)	Promoting circularity within the ICTs. Reducing energy and other resource consumption in the ecosystem through supply chain management.	Enabling circularity through ICT solutions. Reducing energy and other resource consumption in other sectors.	Promoting human centricity, digital inclusion and other values in ICT development. Promoting co-operative ownership and public-private-people partnerships.	Exploiting secure connectivity for life-enhancing services and empowerment for digital inclusion.	Promoting cost reduction and new revenue generation for ICT Supporting developer communities and frugal innovations.	Promoting cost reduction and enabling new revenue generation in other sectors. Providing data for environmental and social development.

Advantages (unique outcomes that enable leveraging long-term value capture, positive externalities among ecosystem stakeholders, and create spillover effects beyond ecosystem boundaries)	Availability and transparency of sustainability reporting data in compliance with environmental sustainability regulations. Optimized operations based on the sustainability data.	Availability and transparency of sustainability reporting data in other sectors. Shared knowledge about the environmental sustainability of products and services to customers for informed decision making and optimizing operations.	Achievement of human values and governance transparency.	Accomplishment of digital inclusion and availability of life-enhancing services while ensuring privacy and security, trustworthiness. Bridging knowledge gaps, fostering a more informed community that encourages collaboration and responsible action.	Access to global businesses with new secure and trustworthy services. New revenue generation for ICT.	Achievement of cost reduction, efficiency improvements, minimizing resource usage. New revenue generation from the use of ICT technologies and services.
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Illustrative example

Next, we provide an illustrative example of the developed framework using the specific joint communications and sensing technology in 6G. This technology can be used to create accurate situation awareness of the surroundings including object detection and tracking in real-time in specific vertical sectors. This in turn can be used to optimize the operations in the given area.

- *Opportunities* in this illustrative example can arise from using joint communications and sensing solutions to create accurate situation awareness including object detection and tracking, which can be used to optimize operations in a specific vertical sector of society to achieve resource efficiency improvement (2nd order environmental sustainability effects). This in turn presents new business opportunities for the 6G vendor (1st order economic sustainability effects) can lead to cost reductions in the vertical sector (2nd order economic sustainability effects). The joint communication and sensing solution can be used to collect environmental sustainability data (2nd order environmental sustainability effects).
- *Value creation* in joint communications and sensing solutions in 6G is possible by the 6G solution providing the awareness of surrounding environment, without the need for additional dedicated sensing devices (1st order environmental effects), while promoting cost reductions in both ICT sector itself (1st order economic sustainability) and other sectors (2nd order economic sustainability).
- Finally, *advantages* in joint communications and sensing solutions can occur through making environmental sustainability reporting data available both within the ICT sector (1st order environmental sustainability effects) and in other sectors (2nd order environmental sustainability effects). Shared knowledge about the environmental sustainability data can enable new services (1st order economic sustainability effects) that ensure privacy and security when provided by the secure 6G solution (2nd order social sustainability effects), providing access to global business (1st and 2nd order economic sustainability effects).

Discussion and impact

This study aims to contribute to the literature that links the business model approach and sustainability in ICT. First, our study proposes a novel framework to investigate how business model antecedents relate to sustainability. We show how business model antecedents, opportunity, value and advantage, relate to first and second-order sustainability effects in practice, and in doing so, we built on the extended definitions of the business model antecedents. Earlier research has shown numerous definitions for opportunity, value and advantage (Foss & Saebi, 2017) but been challenged by how to differentiate between the antecedents at the empirical/practical level. We can consider opportunities as *virtual or potential, situations* that await goal-oriented action such as value creation or capture in an ecosystem of actors. Value creation, in turn, can be considered as something not only potential but *actual* and existing, i.e., establishing premises for positive outcomes in an ecosystem. Finally, advantages can be considered as *intensive*, making a long-term difference and enabling standing out in competition and creating spillover effects beyond ecosystem boundaries.

The presented illustrative example of joint communications and sensing technology in 6G outlined some of the potential interconnections between the first and second order environmental, social, and economic sustainability effects. These interconnections may lead to conflicting trade-offs that require careful consideration, both in practice and in future research. Future research could also examine the linkages between business model antecedents and the sustainability pillars in more detail. In particular, further research is needed in the 6G context to explore sustainable business models for the emerging ecosystems that will form around various future use cases.

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